

WAYS TO USE DIGITAL MARKETING IN SMALL BUSINESS

Kholmamatov Diyor Haqberdievich

Independent Researcher of Samarkand Institute
of Economics and Service, PhD

e-mail: xolmamatov_d@mail.ru

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Abstract: This article presents the theoretical issues of using digital marketing in small business, the main digital marketing channels and instruments, and the analysis of foreign experts' approaches to digital marketing. Reviews of marketing analytics platforms and their role in small businesses.

Keywords: small business, digital marketing, digital marketing channels, digital marketing tools, Marketing Automation, digital marketing technologies.

Introduction

Today's global changes require fundamental changes in business. Goods and services that were in high demand yesterday remain insignificant today. Saturation of markets, high competitive pressure, changes in consumer demands, rapid penetration of innovations increase the need for digital transformation of business.

Digital transformation is the way small businesses introduce new technologies into their business processes, where digital technologies are used to change and improve business operations. Due to this, the scale of small business will expand, become more efficient and profitable.

Digital transformation of small business is aimed at improving the quality of customer service by using new technologies. As one of the new technologies in the digital transformation of small businesses, digital marketing covers the entire business processes of small businesses.

Literature analysis on the topic

As it can be seen from the analysis of scientific literature, different terms are found in the literature. Including "digital marketing", "online marketing", "new marketing", "e-marketing", "internet marketing", "targeted marketing", "interactive marketing" and others. In this regard, local experts Z.A. Khakimov and U.U. Sharifkhodzhayev emphasize that the term "online marketing" is more widely used in the USA, "web marketing" in Italy, "digital marketing" in Great Britain, Russia and many other countries [10]. All of them are aimed at attracting one potential consumer to purchase the company's goods and services. At the same time, in order to bring brands to the market and increase the sales volume of companies, various forms and methods of attracting and retaining customers are used.

In the world of business, the category "digital marketing" has been used since the 1990s. By 2010, the importance of digital marketing tools as a complex to effectively organize deep and close relationships with consumers has increased. The term "digital marketing" was not used until the 1990s and was not mentioned in scientific sources. For the first time, the practice of using digital technologies was carried out by one of the large advertising

companies, SoftAd (now ChannelNet), in order to promote the activities of several car sales companies by distributing hard drives to customers for free.

Approaches to the concept of "digital marketing" have been increasing in recent years. The concept of digital marketing is defined by the American Marketing Association as follows: "digital marketing is a component of marketing that uses the Internet and computers, mobile phones, and other digital technologies that connect to the Internet to promote products and services [7].

Z.A. Khakimov and U.U. Sharifkhodzhayev defined digital marketing as follows: "Digital marketing is reaching customers through the use of digital technologies [10].

Expert Nielsen explains the rapid development of digital marketing and its penetration into people's lives and business processes as follows: "As digital platforms are increasingly integrated into marketing plans and daily life, people are increasingly using digital devices instead of visiting physical stores. As a result, search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing, influencer marketing, content automation, campaign marketing, data-driven marketing, e-commerce marketing, social media marketing (SMM), direct proper email marketing, display advertising, e-books and optical discs have become the norm"[1].

Another expert in digital marketing technology research, Margaret Rose, said digital marketing is beyond the Internet, providing digital media such as television, mobile phones (SMS and MMS), callbacks, and mobile on-hold ringtones. states that it also covers channels [2].

According to sources at the University of Warwick, there are different aspects of digital marketing than online advertising that include offline channels. That is, digital marketing differs from "online advertising" in that it includes some listed non-internet platforms in addition to the Internet [3].

Research methodology

The importance of using digital marketing in small business, the definitions given to digital marketing are systematized based on the method of systematic analysis. The transformation of marketing activities with digital platforms was analyzed based on the analysis methods. Also, monographic observation and abstraction methods are widely used.

Analysis and results

Therefore, the development of technology, especially the emergence of mobile devices and applications, has made business easier in many ways. In addition, consumers are increasingly using their smartphones and tablets to connect with sellers and suppliers and purchase a variety of products from them. Therefore, many small business entities are implementing their marketing and advertising strategies - mainly through direct mail, social networks, mobile phones.

With the advent and continuous development of new technologies and the Internet, small businesses have gained many tools to help them sell their products. Such innovative digital marketing strategies are enabling entrepreneurs to expand their marketing and advertising efforts like never before by reaching larger target audiences, creating relevant and engaging audiences, and better understanding consumer preferences. However, as with any operational strategy, digital marketing requires a lot of attention. Small businesses, in this case, need to analyze and study the needs of their customers, adjust their activities in

accordance with consumer requirements, and at the same time coordinate their strategic goals.

Based on the analysis of scientific literature, the definitions given by foreign experts to digital marketing were studied and summarized in Table 1.

Table 1.1

Definitions of digital marketing by foreign authors

No	Authors	The essence of digital marketing
1.	Fillip Kotler	A set of activities that a company or individual takes online to attract new business and develop brand identity
2.	Ridvan	It is a marketing activity involving a brand that uses a variety of web-based media such as blogs, websites, email, Adwords or social media.
3.	Phillip Kotler and Armstrong	A form of direct marketing that connects consumers with sellers electronically using interactive technologies such as e-mail, websites, online forums and newsgroups, interactive television, mobile communications, etc.
4.	The chartered institute of marketing	It is a management process responsible for identifying, forecasting and profitably meeting customer requirements
5.	Artur Sawicki (world scientific news)	Also called online marketing, it is the promotion of brands to connect with potential customers using the Internet and other forms of digital communication. This includes not only email, social media, and website-based advertising, but also text and multimedia messaging as a marketing channel.
6.	Indrajeet Deshpande	It is an all-encompassing term that consists of digital channels like content marketing, SEO, email marketing, social media marketing, mobile marketing, etc., creating strategies designed to reach and connect with prospects and customers.
7.	AMA (American marketing association)	It is the use of digital or social channels to promote a brand or reach consumers. This type of marketing can be done on the internet, social networks, search engines, mobile devices and other channels. This requires understanding new ways of marketing to consumers and the impact of their behavior.

There are many reasons why effective digital marketing is so important for small businesses today. According to Business Zone [10], digital marketing is the marketing of the future world. Although some traditional methods of advertising and promotion still apply, the truth is that the world today is more connected than ever before through the Internet. This is leading to a proliferation of digital strategies that may one day completely replace more traditional approaches. As more consumers begin to adapt to technological devices, they will naturally expect businesses to adapt as well.

According to Smart Insights [11], as more and more small businesses go digital, they have a great opportunity to gain a competitive advantage. Newly established small business entities that do not yet have a solid reputation in their industry or a loyal customer base may

find the online method useful. Competition combined with the recent economic downturn has shown the importance of digital marketing.

To date, there is no single way to develop a digital marketing strategy. Passion Digital [12] states that digital marketing strategies should be driven by business needs and consumer needs.

Based on the above, it should be noted that digital marketing is the transformation of traditional marketing activities into digital platforms, digital devices, and digital technologies.

In the conditions of globalization and intense competition, one of the main directions of innovative development in the field of marketing is the active use of digital technologies. The Internet, mobile communication, artificial intelligence, information collection and processing systems based on Big Data, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things are increasingly influencing the development of the economy and business processes.

The process of exchange of functions of marketing activities, marketing tools, main activities of marketing with digital marketing is today being confirmed in the practice of all business processes.

As can be seen from Figure 1. above, the exchange (transformation) of marketing theory and art with digital marketing technologies is observed today. We can highlight the following main directions of forming a digital platform to transform marketing activities:

- 1) improvement of digital methods of marketing data collection, processing, analysis;
- 2) organization of interaction with consumers in the digital environment;
- 3) automation of planning and implementation of marketing activities.

The first direction is to improve the methods of collecting, processing and analyzing marketing data. First of all, it is aimed at creating marketing analysis systems, special tools for analyzing marketing data. Examples include web analytics, video analytics, Wi-Fi analytics, data management, and advanced analytics platforms.

Platforms and systems affecting the digital environment
Social media
Social networks (Facebook, Instagram, etc.)
Platforms related to suppliers and consumers (Booking, Momondo, Airbnb)
Services (Yandex, etc.)

Platporm		
Google Analytics		Integrated marketing management
Data management platform		Marketing Research Management
Digital technologies		
Internet	Mobile technologies	
Artificial intelligence	Cloud computing	
Big Data	Internet of Things	

Figure 1. Transformation of marketing activities with digital platforms

The second direction is the organization of interaction with consumers in the digital environment. The main place in marketing activities is the establishment of relations with consumers, that is, relations. It is envisaged to receive consumer objections, receive timely information about their needs and unmet needs on the basis of digital technologies.

The third direction is automation of planning and implementation of marketing activities. Automated marketing (MA - Marketing Automation) applications are used today to work with customers, establish contact with customers, study their needs, and deliver information about goods and services. With automated marketing, businesses communicate with customers via email, web, and social media. This application is also a CRM application.

Digital marketing needs constant improvement and requires a creative approach. Constantly improving digital marketing is the privilege of ensuring the competitiveness of enterprises. This system is not only a means of collecting and analyzing information, but also a means of communication.

When considering the theoretical aspects of the organization of digital marketing, we should pay attention to two basic concepts. The first is digital marketing instruments (tools) and the second is digital marketing channels.

Conclusion

The organization of digital marketing in small business is directly related to digital channels and digital instruments. Digital marketing is rapidly developing in Uzbekistan. IT technologies serve as a catalyst for the formation of new opportunities for the implementation of an effective marketing policy for small businesses.

Currently, it is not necessary to allocate large sums of money for digital marketing, but rather, small business entities need to provide the most basic activity, that is, to provide marketing products with good content on online platforms where buyers are active. Businesses need to perform the most important initial tasks, such as answering customers' questions online, commenting on customers' opinions about the product, and delivering the essence of the brand through digital platforms.

Today, small business entities are finding their place in the market in a short period of time using digital marketing effectively. It is impossible to create marketing management systems in small businesses without using digital technologies. Various divisions of

enterprises related to market activity are constantly increasing and require processed data. In the field of marketing, there is an idea that "the business entity with the best information knows the best markets." This implies the creation of effective marketing information systems. Effective marketing information systems are implemented directly through digital marketing channels.

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